

Spectrophotometric Studies on Fe (II)-2 Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone-ethylenediamine-anil Complex

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Ferrous iron forms a reddish brown coloured complex with 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone-ethylenediamine-anil (HMBEA) in the pH range 2.5-3.0. The complex exhibits maximum absorption at 520 nm and 480 nm. The composition of the complex (1:1) has been determined by Job's method of continuous variation, mole ratio method and slope ratio method employing spectrophotometric data. The dissociation constant and the stability constant at 30° are 5.775×10^{-7} and 1.732×10^8 , respectively. The standard free energy of formation of the complex is -8.706 kcal/mole and the molecular extinction coefficient is 8.3×10^3 at 520 nm. The quantitative estimation of Fe^{2+} at pH 2.5-3.0 was done and the composition of the complex (1:1) was established by oxide method also.

THE 2-hydroxy - 5 - methyl - benzophenone-ethylene-diamine-anil(HMBEA) behaves as a complexing agent for a number of transition metal ions. However so far no spectrophotometric studies of its metal chelates have been carried out. The present work deals with the spectrophotometric study of the complex formation of ferrous ion with HMBEA reagent. The reagent was synthesized by considering 2 - hydroxy - 5 - methyl-benzophenone with ethylenediamine. The composition of the complex was studied by Job's method of continuous variation^{2,3}, Yoe and Jone's mole ratio method⁴ and Harvey and Manning's slope ratio method.⁵

Experimental

A stock solution of ferrous sulphate(0.01 M) was prepared and was standardized gravimetrically as the oxide. From this stock solution, solutions of required strengths were prepared freshly.

Preparation of 2 - hydroxy - 5 - methyl - benzophenone - ethylenediamine - anil (HMBEA) :

The 2 hydroxy - 5 - methyl-benzophenone¹(2 moles) was condensed with ethylenediamine (1 mole) in presence of absolute alcohol by refluxing the mixtures for 1 hr. The yellow anil formed was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 199°

Found : C-80.32; H-6.23; N-6.22%

Calc. for
($C_{30}H_{28}N_2O_2$) C-80.36; H-6.25; N-6.25%

Reaction with Fe^{2+} ions : A one percent ethanolic solution of the reagent was used. It gave reddish brown precipitate with Fe^{2+} at pH 2.5-3.0.

Estimation of iron : A definite amount of Fe^{2+} solution (0.01 M) was taken and diluted. The pH was adjusted to 2.5-3.0 and required amount of reagent solution (0.01 M) in alcohol was added with stirring and little excess of the reagent solution was added to

ensure complete precipitation. The precipitates were digested at about 60°-70° for half an hour and filtered, washed, dried and weighed as $Fe(C_{30}H_{28}N_2O_2)$. The results are recorded in Table 1. It has been found that Cu, Ni, Co, Al, Zn, Mn, do not interfere at this pH condition. The complex are crystallised from alcohol.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF Fe^{2+} AT pH 2.5-3.0

S. N.	Fe^{2+} taken in mg	Fe^{2+} complex in mg	Fe^{2+} found in mg	Error in mg
1	5.6	47.6	5.3	-0.3
2	8.4	76.4	8.5	+0.1
3	11.2	97.9	10.9	-0.3
4	14.0	124.0	13.8	-0.2

Oxide-method : A definite amount of the complex was ignited and converted to oxide and weighed as Fe_2O_3 and percentage iron was calculated. The nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldhals method. 0.5018 g complex on ignition gave 0.0796 g Fe_2O_3 which is corresponding to 0.0556g Fe^{2+} when required is 0.0558 g Fe^{2+} .

Found : N=5.4%

Calc. for $Fe(C_{30}H_{28}N_2O_2)$ N=5.6%

The molecular weight determined. Cryoscopically suggested it to be a monomer and hence the composition of the complex is 1.1.

Spectrophotometric study : The equimolar solutions of ferrous sulphate and reagent (HMBEA) in the ratio of 2:1, 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 at pH 2.5-3.0 were mixed and the final volume was made 20 ml by adding required amount of water and alcohol to keep alcohol-water composition same in all cases. The absorption spectra of all the solutions taken. In all cases the maximum absorptions were found to be at 520 nm and 480 nm suggest that reagent forms only one type of complex with Fe^{2+} ion.

Composition of the complex :

Job's method : A series of the solutions was prepared by mixing X ml of $(1.0 \times 10^{-4} M)$ reagent HMBEA solution with (2X) ml of $(1.0 \times 10^{-4} M)$ Ferrous sulphate solution at pH 2.5-3.0 and making the final volume of the mixtures to 10 ml by adding required amount of alcohol and water so that alcohol water composition in all solutions remains same. The optical densities were measured at 520 nm and 480 nm. Since the absorption due to ferrous sulphate and of the reagent at the wavelength under consideration was negligible, the optical densities were plotted against the composition of the solutions. The curve showed peak when the mole ratio of the metal to the ligand was 1 : 1.

Mole ratio method : The composition of the complex in solution was also determined by the mole ratio method. Equimolar solutions of the reagent $(1 \times 10^{-4} M)$ HMBEA and $(1 \times 10^{-4} M)$ Ferrous sulphate were taken. A series of solutions was prepared by mixing a definite amount of Fe^{2+} ion solution (1 ml) with varying amounts of reagent solution (from 0.2 to 3.0 ml) or vice-versa and the final volume was made to 10 ml by adding required alcohol and water to keep the alcohol water composition same in all cases. The optical densities were measured at 520 nm and plotted against the mole ratio. The plot (Fig 1) obtained by plotting absorbancies of the solutions in which reagent was variable, shows that upto molar composition of 1 : 1, it is a straight line and thereafter it bends suggesting that the composition of the complex is 1 : 1.

Fig. 1 : Molar composition of Ferrous HMBEA complex at pH 2.5-3.0 by mole ratio method at 520 nm. [1.0 ml of $(1.0 \times 10^{-4} M)$ $FeSO_4$ solution and varying amounts of HMBEA $(1.0 \times 10^{-4} M)$ were mixed and the final volume made upto 10 ml]

Slope ratio method : Two series of solutions were prepared from equimolar solutions of iron $(1 \times 10^{-4} M)$ and of reagent $(1 \times 10^{-4} M)$. In one series, the concentration of the iron was varied from 0.2 to 1.0 ml keeping the concentration of the reagent constant (5.0 ml) and un excess. In second series the concentration of the reagent was variable (0.2 ml to 1.0 ml) when the concentration of iron was kept constant (5 ml) and in excess. The absorbancies were measured at 520 nm and were plotted against the concentration of the variable. The plots (Fig. 2) obtained are parallel lines having slopes of same value indicating 1 : 1 complex.

Fig. 2 : Molar composition of Ferrous (HMBEA) complex at pH 2.5-3.0 by slope ratio method at 520 nm. [(A) $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ $FeSO_4$ (0.2 to 1.0 ml) were added to 5 ml of HMBEA $(1.0 \times 10^{-4} M)$ and (B) $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ HMBEA (0.2 to 1.0 ml) were added to 5 ml $FeSO_4$ $(1.0 \times 10^{-4} M)$. Final volume in each case was 10 ml.]

Determination of equilibrium and dissociation constants : The dissociation of the complex is represented as

where α is the degree of dissociation and C is concentration of the complex. The dissociation constant is given by

$$K_d = \frac{(\alpha C)(n\alpha C)^n}{C(1-\alpha)}$$

But for 1 : 1 complex, $n=1$, hence

$$K_d = \alpha^2 C / 1 - \alpha$$

The value of α may be obtained from Fig. 2 by the relation

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m}$$

where E_m and E_s have usual meanings.

$$\text{Thus } \alpha = \frac{0.1967 - 0.1660}{0.1967} = 0.1561$$

Therefore $K_d = 5.775 \times 10^{-7}$ and the stability constant is 1.732×10^6 .

The equilibrium constant can also be calculated

from the relation
$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-x)}$$

where a and b are the concentration of ferrous ion and of the reagent which are known. The concentration x of the complex after adding the reagent can be calculated by using observed absorbance and molar extinction coefficient. The equilibrium constant values, calculated on the assumption of (1 : 1) n=1, (1 : 2) n=2 are given in Table 2. The values are constant for n=1. The molar extinction coefficient is equal to the slope of the parallel lines in slope ratio method which was found to be equal to 8.4×10^3 which agrees with the value of 8.3×10^3 calculated from the plot of mole ratio method. The average value of equilibrium constant is 1.732×10^6

and the standard free energy of formation (ΔF°) of the complex is calculated from the relation

$$\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K$$

is found to be -8.706 Kcal/mole at 30°

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TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS CALCULATED FROM MOLE RATIO METHOD

Moles of reagent added/mole of Fe	K (n=1)	K (n=2)
0.1	1.761×10^6	3.045×10^{10}
0.2	1.706×10^6	1.770×10^{10}
0.3	1.755×10^6	1.322×10^{10}
0.4	1.717×10^6	1.166×10^{10}
0.5	1.723×10^6	1.124×10^{10}
	mean K = 1.732×10^6	